

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

D6.4: Information material for scientists and public no.1

WP6 – Communication, dissemination and exploitation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Document Information

Grant Agreement	771738	Acronym	NextFOOD	
Full Project Title	Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system			
Start Date	15/03/2018	Duration	48	
Project URL	https://www.nextfood-project.eu			
Deliverable	D6.4: Information material for scientists and public no.1			
Working Package	WP6 – Working Package Title Here			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	30/10/2019	Actual	30/10/2019
Nature	R – Report etc.	Dissemination Level	P - Public	
WP Leader	Name of WP Leader Here			
Authors	Evdokia Krystalidou			
Contributors	Martin Melin			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.1		Draft		
0.2		Draft		
1.0		Final	Review	

Table of Contents

Executive summary.....	4
1 Brochure.....	5
2 Poster.....	6
3 Project Presentation.....	7
4 Banner.....	8
5 Flyer	9
6 Website and Social Media	10
6.1 Website.....	10
6.2 Facebook.....	10
6.3 Instagram.....	11
6.4 Twitter	12
6.5 YouTube Channel	12

Executive summary

The Current deliverable presents the Information material for scientists and public no.1. The material has been printed and distributed to partners for dissemination by the lead beneficiary of WP6: AFS.

1 Brochure

Partners

- Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
- Lund University
- University of Oradea
- University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice
- Norwegian University of Life Sciences
- American Farm School
- Alma Mater Studiorum - University of Bologna
- Bioinstitut
- Forestry Research Institute of Sweden
- Agronutritional Consortium Of The Region Of Central Macedonia
- International Center for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies
- German World Hunger Aid
- Sekem Development Foundation
- Mekelle University
- Alexander Technological Educational Institute of Thessaloniki
- European Association for Integrating Food Science and Engineering Knowledge into the Food Chain
- Roskilde University
- University of Gastronomic Sciences
- University of Chile

follow us on

www.nextfood-project.eu
info@nextfood-project.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

What is NextFOOD?

NextFOOD is an International project funded by Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme that started in 2018 and will last until 2022.

NextFOOD will drive the crucial transition to more sustainable and competitive agrifood and forestry systems development by designing and implementing education and training systems to prepare budding or already practising professionals with competencies to push the green shift in our rapidly changing society.

Goal

To generate an innovative European science and education road map for sustainable agriculture and forestry along the value chain from research via production into application.

Objectives

- ✎ Create an inventory of the skills and competencies needed for a transition to more sustainable agriculture, forestry and associated bio-value chains
- ✎ Facilitate case studies to identify gaps and needs
- ✎ Test new relevant curricula and training methods
- ✎ Identify policy instruments that support the transition towards action-, and practice-oriented learning methods
- ✎ Peer-review tools for evaluating the quality of the practice-oriented research
- ✎ Create a platform for knowledge sharing

Actions

- ✎ Development of **Inventory of skills** needed for a transition to more sustainable agriculture, forestry and associated bio-value chains
- ✎ **Action Research Facilitation** to enhance participatory innovation processes. Facilitation of a number of case studies that are in a transition to participatory, action-directed learning in agrifood systems, and in the range from vocational training to university studies
- ✎ **Future curriculum for an Action-Oriented, Participatory Education** and training systems to spur innovative development within formal education and informal training strategies related to agrifood systems
- ✎ **Policy Recommendations** on a regional, national and EU-level for education and training systems for farmers, forest professionals, advisers and others, that will support action and help address challenges in the improvement of sustainability of agrifood systems
- ✎ **Quality assurance for practice-oriented research** output and development of a list of the best practices of standards and criteria for quality assessment of practice-oriented research and education

TRANSFORMATIVE AND PARTICIPATORY LEARNING MODEL

COLLABORATIVE AND ACTION-ORIENTED LEARNING

NextFOOD is facilitating co-creation of innovation and knowledge in agriculture, forestry and related bio-value chains to overcome obstacles preventing efficient implementation of innovative techniques and methods in the agrifood and forestry sectors. Cultivating five competencies: **observation, reflection, participation, dialogue, and visioning**, to educate lifelong learners in agrifood systems. By preparing farmers, students, advisors and others to become lifelong learners and acquire the soft and the technical skills needed to go from knowledge to action, NextFOOD will boost the transition to a more sustainable and competitive food and forest production.

2 Poster

Next FOOD

Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

follow us on

www.nextfood-project.eu | info@nextfood-project.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

3 Project Presentation

The logo for 'Next FOOD' is displayed in white on a dark grey background. 'Next' is in a clean, sans-serif font. 'FOOD' is in a larger, bold, distressed font. A stylized green leaf with two smaller leaves is positioned above the 'O's in 'FOOD'.

Next
FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT
GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS
IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

What is NEXTFOOD?

NextFOOD is an International project funded by Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme that started in 2018 and will last until 2022

Will drive the crucial transition to more **sustainable and competitive agrifood and forestry systems** development by designing and implementing education and training systems to prepare budding or already practicing professionals with competencies to push the green shift in our rapidly changing society

EUROPEAN UNION

A consortium of 19 Partners

Europe	Africa	Latin America

Objectives

Overall aim: To generate an innovative European science and education road map for sustainable agriculture and forestry along the value chain from research via production into application.

Objectives:

- Create an **inventory of the skills** and competencies needed for a transition to more sustainable agriculture, forestry and associated bio-value chains
- Facilitate **case studies** to identify gaps and needs
- Test new relevant curricula and **training methods**
- Identify **policy instruments** that support the transition towards action-, and practice-oriented learning methods
- **Peer-review tools** for evaluating quality of the practice-oriented research
- Create a platform for **knowledge sharing**

Action-learning

In 2018 it was agreed to use methodology based on case studies using as a reference the action-learning model adapted from Lieblen *et al* (2012), which seeks to generate a close link between University and Society.

TRANSFORMATIVE AND PARTICIPATORY LEARNING MODEL

COLLABORATIVE AND ACTION-ORIENTED LEARNING

Work Packages (WPs)

WP7
Project Management

Key skills for sustainable agrifood and forestry systems

WP1
Inventory of skills

WP3
Action-Oriented, Participatory Education and training systems

Hindering and supporting forces action-oriented, participatory training

WP4
Policy Recommendations for education and training

Models, good examples & best practice

Action-oriented and participatory case studies

WP5
Quality assurance for practice-oriented research output

Test of framework for peer-review evaluation on cases

WP2
Action Research Facilitation

Supporting, monitoring and facilitating

WP6
Stakeholder Involvement + Collaboration and learning within consortium + Dissemination of results beyond consortium

Case Studies

The project has adopted a case oriented approach

The case development will rest on an iterative, participatory process consisting of:

1. Observation and description of the current situation in each case.
2. Visioning of a desired future state.
3. Analysis to identify key issues, solutions, supporting and hindering forces, etc.
4. Elaboration and discussion of action plans.
5. Implementation of plans.
6. Iteration of this process.

Case Studies

- **Case 1.** Agroecology and sustainable farming systems (**Norway**)
- **Case 2.** Students and farmers taking food innovation from idea to market (**Romania**)
- **Case 3.** Learning from farmers Training Centres: Multi-stakeholder action learning Platform (**Ethiopia**)
- **Case 4.** Supply Chain Innovation competition (**Austria**)
- **Case 5.** Action learning Agriscapes (**Greece**)
- **Case 6.** Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain (**Sweden**)
- **Case 7.** Agroecology: action learning in farming and food systems (**Czech Republic**)
- **Case 8.** Experiential and action learning in sustainable gastronomy (**Italy**)
- **Case 9.** Improving sustainability in farming and food systems by bringing in agroecological approach through action learning (**India**)
- **Case 10.** Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system (**Egypt**)

Case Studies

Each case study is different depending on its objectives, but all of them are united by the application of one strategy: **participatory education** in educational systems and professionals training. This is centered in the acquirement of competencies like:

- Observation
- Dialogue
- Vision (principles)
- Reflection

Cross-cutting processes

Find more about us...

info@nextfood-project.eu

4 Banner

Next FOOD

Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Driving the green shift to more sustainable and competitive agrifood and forestry systems
 Designing and implementing learner-centric, participatory, action-based and action-oriented education and training

www.nextfood-project.eu
info@nextfood-project.eu

follow us on

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

5 Flyer

Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Driving the green shift to more sustainable and competitive agrifood and forestry systems
Designing and implementing learner-centric, participatory, action-based and action-oriented education and training

Follow us on

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

Goal

To generate an innovative European science and education road map for sustainable agriculture and forestry along the value chain from research via production into application.

Objectives

- Create an inventory of the skills and competencies needed for a transition to more sustainable agriculture, forestry and associated bio-value chains
- Facilitate case studies to identify gaps and needs
- Test new relevant curricula and training methods
- Identify policy instruments that support the transition towards action-, and practice-oriented learning methods
- Peer-review tools for evaluating the quality of the practice-oriented research
- Create a platform for knowledge sharing

www.nextfood-project.eu | info@nextfood-project.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 771738

The present Deliverable reflects only the author's view and the Research Executive Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

6 Website and Social Media

6.1 Website

<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/>

6.2 Facebook

<https://www.facebook.com/nextfoodinnovativescienceandeducation/>

6.3 Instagram

The screenshot shows the Instagram profile for 'nextfoodproject'. The profile picture is the NextFOOD logo. The bio includes the text: 'nextfoodproject', '52 δημοσιεύσεις', '232 ακόλουθοι', 'Ακολουθείτε 342 χρήστες', 'NextFood', 'Innovative Science & Education for Sustainable Agriculture #eu_h2020', '@europeancommission #horizon2020', and 'www.nextfood-project.eu'. Below the bio are two featured posts: 'Platform' and 'EU_H2020'. The main grid shows six posts: a 'NextFOOD PLATFORM' subscription card, a '2019 FOOD FAIR Sustainable Sup International Stu Competition' poster, a '10 Questions about skills for the future of sustainable food and forestry: NextFOOD' poster, a photo of a solar panel in a field, a photo of a construction site with a sign in French, and a photo of a man speaking at a podium with a NextFOOD logo.

<https://www.instagram.com/nextfoodproject/>

6.4 Twitter

<https://twitter.com/NextFood3>

6.5 YouTube Channel

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCeJsZeXhtM_S3kju-iWLUww